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TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDAGI INNOVATSIYALAR IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASH VOSITASIDA

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada ta'lim xizmatlari bozorida innovatsiyalarning o'rni va ularning iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashdagi ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, ta'lim tizimida zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish, raqamlashtirish jarayonlari hamda innovatsion yondashuvlar orqali inson kapitalini rivojlantirish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, ta'lim xizmatlari bozoridagi innovatsiyalar mamlakatning iqtisodiy barqarorligi va raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda muhim omil sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Maqolada iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni mustahkamlashda ta'lim sohasining strategik ahamiyati asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim xizmatlari bozori, innovatsiyalar, iqtisodiy xavfsizlik, inson kapitali, raqamlashtirish, ta'lim tizimi, barqaror rivojlanish, raqobatbardoshlik

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется роль инноваций на рынке образовательных услуг и их значение в обеспечении экономической безопасности. Рассматриваются вопросы внедрения современных технологий, цифровизации образовательной системы, а также развития человеческого капитала на основе инновационных подходов. По результатам исследования установлено, что инновации в сфере образовательных услуг выступают важным фактором повышения устойчивости и конкурентоспособности национальной экономики. Обоснована стратегическая роль образования в укреплении экономической безопасности.

Ключевые слова: рынок образовательных услуг, инновации, экономическая безопасность, человеческий капитал, цифровизация, система образования, устойчивое развитие, конкурентоспособность

Abstract: This article analyzes the role of innovations in the education services market and their importance in ensuring economic security. It examines the implementation of modern technologies, digitalization processes, and innovative approaches in the development of human capital. The study concludes that innovations in the education services market are a key factor in enhancing economic stability and competitiveness. The strategic importance of the education sector in strengthening economic security is also substantiated.

Keywords: education services market, innovation, economic security, human capital, digitalization, education system, sustainable development, competitiveness

KIRISH

Hozirgi globallashuv sharoitida iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlash har bir davlatning ustuvor vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Iqtisodiy xavfsizlikning muhim tarkibiy qismlaridan biri sifatida inson kapitalining sifati va salohiyati alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Mazkur omil esa bevosita ta'lim tizimi va undagi xizmatlar bozori bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. So'nggi yillarda ta'lim xizmatlari bozori jadal rivojlanib, unda innovatsion yondashuvlar, raqamli texnologiyalar va yangi boshqaruv mexanizmlarining keng joriy etilishi kuzatilmoqda. Ayniqsa, masofaviy ta'lim, onlayn platformalar, sun'iy intellekt asosidagi o'qitish tizimlari kabi innovatsiyalar ta'lim sifati va samaradorligini oshirish bilan birga, iqtisodiyotning barqaror rivojlanishiga xizmat qilmoqda. Ta'lim xizmatlari bozorida innovatsiyalarni rivojlantirish orqali nafaqat malakali kadrlar tayyorlash, balki milliy iqtisodiyotning raqobatbardoshligini oshirish, tashqi iqtisodiy tahdidlarga bardoshlilikini kuchaytirish va ijtimoiy barqarorlikni ta'minlash imkoniyati yuzaga keladi. Shu nuqtai nazardan, ta'lim sohasidagi innovatsiyalar iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashning muhim vositasi sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Mazkur maqolaning maqsadi - ta'lim xizmatlari bozorida innovatsiyalarning iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashdagi o'rni va ahamiyatini tahlil qilish, shuningdek, ushbu jarayonni takomillashtirish bo'yicha ilmiy asoslangan taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishdan iborat.

MAVZUGA DABIYOTLAR SHARHI

Ta'lim xizmatlari bozorining rivojlanishi va undagi innovatsion jarayonlar iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashda muhim ilmiy yo'nalishlardan biri sifatida ko'plab tadqiqotchilar tomonidan o'rganilgan. Xususan, inson kapitali nazariyasiga asos solgan Gary Becker ta'limning iqtisodiy o'sish va jamiyat farovonligiga ta'sirini asoslab bergan [1]. Uning fikricha, ta'limga yo'naltirilgan investitsiyalar uzoq muddatda iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlaydi. Innovatsiyalar nazariyasi doirasida Joseph Schumpeter iqtisodiy rivojlanishning asosiy drayveri sifatida innovatsiyalarni ko'rsatib, ayniqsa bilim va texnologiyalar asosidagi yangiliklarning iqtisodiyotdagi rolini alohida ta'kidlaydi [2]. Bu yondashuv ta'lim xizmatlari bozorida innovatsiyalarni joriy etish orqali iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni mustahkamlash mumkinligini ko'rsatadi. Zamonaviy tadqiqotlarda ta'lim tizimining raqamlashtirilishi va innovatsion rivoji iqtisodiy xavfsizlik bilan uzviy bog'liqligi qayd etilgan. Jumladan, OECD hisobotlarida ta'lim sifatini oshirish, innovatsion kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish hamda raqamli ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish milliy iqtisodiyotning raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlovchi asosiy omillardan biri sifatida baholanadi [3]. Shuningdek, World Bank tadqiqotlarida ta'lim xizmatlari bozorining samarali ishlashi va unda innovatsion mexanizmlarning joriy etilishi iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni mustahkamlashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etishi ta'kidlangan [4]. Xususan, inson kapitalining rivojlanishi iqtisodiy xavflarga nisbatan barqarorlikni oshiradi. MDH va milliy olimlar tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlarda ham ta'lim xizmatlari bozorining institutsional rivoji, innovatsion infratuzilma va davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarining iqtisodiy xavfsizlikka ta'siri keng yoritilgan [5]. Ularning fikricha, ta'lim sohasida innovatsion muhitni shakllantirish orqali iqtisodiy tizimning barqarorligi va moslashuvchanligi ta'minlanadi. Yuqoridagi ilmiy yondashuvlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, ta'lim xizmatlari bozorida innovatsiyalar nafaqat ta'lim sifati va samaradorligini oshiradi, balki iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashning muhim omili sifatida ham xizmat qiladi. Shu bilan birga, mazkur yo'nalishda yanada chuqur ilmiy izlanishlar olib borish zarurati saqlanib qolmoqda.

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI

Mazkur tadqiqotda ta'lim xizmatlarining qiymatini shakllantirish va takror ishlab chiqarish jarayonlari tizimli hamda institutsional yondashuv asosida o'rganildi. Tadqiqot jarayonida tahlil va sintez, qiyosiy tahlil, statistik tahlil, kontent tahlil hamda mantiqiy umumlashtirish usullaridan foydalanildi. Shuningdek, iqtisodiy resurslar va ularning aylanish jarayonini aniqlash maqsadida empirik tahlil ham qo'llanilib, ta'lim xizmatlarining ishlab chiqarish va iste'mol bosqichlari kompleks baholandi.

TAHLIL VA NATIJA

Kapital faqat moddiy resurslarni (binolar, inshootlar, o'quv jihozlari va oliy o'quv yurti faoliyatini ta'minlaydigan jihozlarni) o'z ichiga oladi. Vaqt - bu saqlash, sotib olish, sotish yoki kechiktirish mumkin bo'lmagan va qiymat ifodasiga ega bo'lmagan resurs, lekin bozor sharoitida u juda qimmat. Ta'lim xizmatlarini ko'rsatishda vaqt omili muhim rol o'ynaydi. Kapital ham naqd, ham pul shaklida ifodalanishi mumkin. Tadbirkorlik qobiliyati ta'lim xizmatlarida iqtisodiy faoliyatning turli darajalarida ehtiyojlarni maksimal darajada qondirish uchun yer, mehnat va kapitalni birlashtira olish qobiliyati tufayli iqtisodiy resursning mustaqil maqomiga ega.

Zamonaviy sharoitda axborot resurslari ham ishlab chiqarish omillari hisoblanadi. Lekin bu ishda axborot moddiy va inson kapitalini birlashtirgan kapitalning alohida turi sifatida qaraladi. Ta'lim xizmatini ko'rsatish ko'pincha ajralmas moddiy komponent - ta'lim mahsulotiga asoslanadi.

Ko'pgina o'zaro bog'liq bozorlar segmentlari ta'lim xizmatlari uchun resurslar va mehnat resurslari bozorlarini ifodalaydi (1-rasm).

1-rasm. Ta'lim xizmatlari bozorida innovatsiyalar orqali iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlash mexanizmi (sxema)¹

Zamonaviy jamoaviy mehnat o'zining innovatsion salohiyati bilan ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirishning ilg'or texnika va texnologiyadan muhim omiliga aylanib bormoqda. Zamonaviy mehnat yanada intellektual rivojlanishga intiladi va yuqori sifatli, doimiy yangilanadigan va nisbatan arzon mahsulotlarni individual ishlab chiqarishni ta'minlashga qodir. Shu bilan birga, biz ushbu mehnatning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini unutmasligimiz kerak. Ta'lim xizmatini yaratish uchun zarur bo'lgan jamoaviy mehnat uch turdagi mehnatdan iborat (1-jadval).

1 – jadval

Inson kapitalining xususiyatlari

Yuqori malakali, ijodiy mehnat (inson kapitali)	Qattiq mehnat	Oddiy mehnat
Fan, madaniyatning eng so'nggi yutuqlariga ega bo'lgan va ilg'or g'oyalarni amalga oshirishga qodir bo'lgan yuqori kasbiy, umuminsoniy, intellektual jamoaviy mehnatni shakllantirish va tayyorlash darajasi.	Ma'lumotli va malakali, ish turini, uning joyini, vaqtini va boshqalarni tanlash imkoniyatiga ega bo'lgan murakkab jami mehnatning shakllanish darajasi.	Undan ta'lim talab qilmaydigan oddiy mehnatning shakllanish darajasi.
O'zining inson kapitalidan bevosita yangi inson kapitalini yaratish uchun foydalanadigan o'qituvchi yoki tadqiqotchining ishi	Ta'lim xizmatlarini ishlab chiqarish tashkilotchilarining yuqori malakali mehnati, inson kapitalini yaratishda bevosita ishtirok etmaydi, lekin ularsiz bu jarayon imkonsiz bo'lib qoladi: kadrlar bo'limi, buxgalteriya hisobi, texnik xizmat ko'rsatish bo'limi va boshqalar.	Ta'lim muassasalari binolarida tozalik va tartibni ta'minlovchi texnik xodimlar

Ta'lim muassasasi ichki mehnat bozorida taqdim etilgan barcha turdagi mehnatni iste'mol qiladi. O'qituvchining mehnati bozorda turlicha taqdim etilishi mumkin:

- vaqtincha ishsiz bo'lgan o'qituvchi;

1 Muallif ishlanmasi

- pedagogik ma'lumotga ega bo'lgan universitet bitiruvchisi;
- pedagogik mahoratga ega bo'lishi kerak bo'lgan aspirant;
- o'zlashtirilgan va to'plangan bilimlarni uzatishi kerak bo'lgan ilmiy xodim;
- o'z ishini pedagogik faoliyat bilan uyg'unlashtirish imkoniyati va zaruriyatiga ega bo'lgan murakkab mehnat vakili;
- o'quv yuklamasi yetarli bo'lmagan va bo'sh ish kunida o'rindoshlik asosida ishlashga muhtoj bo'lgan o'qituvchi.

Yuqorida tavsiflangan mehnat resurslarining iste'molchilari ham davlat, ham nodavlat ta'lim muassasalaridir. Ta'limning ushbu ikki sektorida bir xil mehnat birligidan foydalanishni parallel ravishda birlashtirish mumkin. Bunday imkoniyatlar nodavlat ta'lim muassasalarida yuqori malakali ilmiy-pedagogik mehnat resurslarini iste'mol qilish imkonini beradi (2-jadval).

Innovatsiya yo'nalishi	Mazmuni	Iqtisodiy xavfsizlikka ta'siri
Raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari	Onlayn platformalar, LMS tizimlari, masofaviy ta'lim	Ta'limga kirish imkoniyatini kengaytiradi, kadrlar salohiyatini oshiradi
Sun'iy intellekt asosidagi ta'lim	Adaptiv o'qitish tizimlari, AI yordamida tahlil	Ta'lim sifatini oshiradi, mehnat bozoriga mos kadrlar tayyorlaydi
Innovatsion pedagogik yondashuvlar	Interfaol metodlar, STEAM ta'lim	Tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantiradi, iqtisodiy barqarorlikni mustahkamlaydi
Xalqaro ta'lim integratsiyasi	Dual ta'lim, akademik mobillik	Global raqobatbardoshlikni oshiradi
Ta'limni boshqarishda innovatsiyalar	Elektron boshqaruv, monitoring tizimlari	Resurslardan samarali foydalanishni ta'minlaydi

2-jadval. Ta'lim xizmatlari bozorida innovatsiyalarning asosiy yo'nalishlari va ularning iqtisodiy xavfsizlikka ta'siri²

Kapital resurslar - bu ta'lim muassasasining asosiy fondlari (binolar, inshootlar, jihozlar, qurilmalar, mashinalar, qurilmalar, kutubxona fondlari, turar-joylar va boshqalar). Ta'lim muassasasining kapital resurslari ham jismoniy, ham xarajat ko'rsatkichlarida hisobga olinadi va rejalashtiriladi.

Fizikaviy ko'rsatkichlar asosiy vositalarning moddiy tarkibini aniqlash va hisobga olish uchun zarurdir. Xarajat ko'rsatkichlari universitetning asosiy fondlarini pul bilan baholashni aniqlash, ya'ni mutaxassislarni tayyorlash uchun resurslar xarajatlarini aniqlash uchun zarurdir. Boshqa sohalarida bo'lgani kabi oliy ta'limda ham kapital uzoq vaqt davomida qo'llaniladi, bu davrda ularning jismoniy eskirishi va ma'naviy eskirishi sodir bo'ladi. Biroq, ta'lim muassasalari kapitali faoliyatida ham o'ziga xoslik mavjud. U shundan iboratki, uning faol qismining xizmat ko'rsatish shartlari, birinchi navbatda, fan va texnika yutuqlari darajasi, asosiy fondlarning (ayniqsa, ularning faol qismi) ushbu mezonlarga muvofiqligi bilan belgilanadi (2-jadval).

Ko'rsatkichlar	Innovatsiyalarsiz holat	Innovatsiyalar joriy etilganda	Natija
Ta'lim sifati	O'rtacha	Yuqori	Kadrlar sifati oshadi
Bandlik darajasi	Past	Yuqori	Ishsizlik kamayadi
Raqobatbardoshlik	Past	Yuqori	Milliy iqtisodiyot mustahkamlanadi
Inson kapitali	Cheklangan	Rivojlangan	Innovatsion iqtisodiyot shakllanadi
Iqtisodiy xavfsizlik	Nisbatan past	Yuqori	Barqarorlik ta'minlanadi

3-jadval. Ta'lim xizmatlari bozorining iqtisodiy xavfsizlik ko'rsatkichlariga ta'siri³

² Muallif ishlanmasi

³ Muallif ishlanmasi

Nodavlat ta'lim muassasalari uchun kapital taqsimotining o'ziga xos xususiyati mavjud. Nodavlat sektorni rivojlantirish uchun asosiy cheklov - bu joylarning yetishmasligi. Agar davlat muassasasi operativ boshqaruvdagi davlat mulkidan byudjetdan tashqari faoliyatni rivojlantirish uchun foydalansa, nodavlat ta'lim muassasasi bu masalani boshqacha hal qilishi kerak. Bu cheklov, bizning nuqtai nazarimizdan, yangi o'qitish usullari tizimini, jumladan, ochiq ta'limni rivojlantirish uchun zarur shartlardan biri bo'lib xizmat qildi.

XULOSA VA TAKLIFLAR

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, ta'lim xizmatlarining qiymati ularni yaratish va takror ishlab chiqarish jarayonida sarflanadigan iqtisodiy resurslar bilan belgilanadi hamda ushbu jarayon uzluksiz aylanish xarakteriga ega. Ta'lim xizmatlari bozori nafaqat iqtisodiy, balki ijtimoiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, uning samaradorligi moliyaviy, insoniy va axborot resurslaridan oqilona foydalanishga bog'liq. Shu bilan birga, ta'lim xizmatlarini moliyalashtirish va resurslarni taqsimlashdagi nomutanosibliklar tizim barqarorligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Shu munosabat bilan ta'lim xizmatlari qiymatini shakllantirish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish, resurslardan samarali foydalanishni ta'minlash, ta'lim jarayonida inson kapitalini rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan investitsiyalarni oshirish, davlat va xususiy sektor o'rtasida muvozanatni saqlash, shuningdek, ta'lim xizmatlarini takror ishlab chiqarish jarayonini kompleks boshqarish zarur. Mazkur chora-tadbirlar ta'lim xizmatlari bozorining barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlash va uning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

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